

EFFECTIVENESS OF CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENT YOUTH

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Abstract. This article highlights the role and effectiveness of cultural and educational activities in developing the spiritual and moral education of student youth in higher educational institutions. It analyzes the use of national values as the main criterion in the educational system, involving students in collective work, and creating a healthy environment among them.

Keywords: spirituality, morality, students, upbringing, cultural and educational events, higher education

Introduction. One of the main directions of today's educational policy is nurturing spiritually mature, morally upright youth with respect for national values. The effectiveness of this process in higher educational institutions largely depends on the organized cultural and educational activities.

Main body. Cultural and educational activities are not only meaningful ways for students to spend their free time but also important educational tools that influence their worldview, thinking, social activity, and moral perspectives. Specifically, through theatrical performances, spirituality days, meetings with prominent figures, creative evenings, and reading competitions, positive feelings and a sense of duty and responsibility are fostered in the hearts of students. The role of the Deputy Dean for Youth Affairs in effectively organizing such events is extremely important. They actively engage students, identify the most talented among them, and create conditions for the realization of their talents. Thus, students live with the desire to be useful to society while demonstrating their potential.

Conclusion

The role of cultural and educational events in the upbringing of student youth is invaluable. Through these events, they realize their identity, understand the essence of values, and live with a sense of national pride. The Deputy Dean's leadership, innovative approach, and organizational capacity in this area serve to raise young people as a healthy, active, and harmoniously developed generation.

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